

Reaction of Phenylene Diamines with Phenacyl Bromide

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Arrhenius parameters have been determined for the reaction of aniline, ortho-, meta- and para-phenylene diamines (PDA) with phenacyl bromide in nitrobenzene. The amino group at ortho- position of aniline does not alter the rate to a great extent possibly due to a hydrogen bonded structure. The meta- and para-isomers increase the rate to a very great extent with considerable change in the value of energy of activation. The reaction has also been studied in a number of solvents and an attempt has been made to correlate the solvent effect.

The reaction of phenacyl bromide with bases has attracted the attention of several workers. Rout *et al*¹ from their researches have proposed a mechanism basing on direct SN² displacement. The carbonyl group merely acts as an activating group. It was, therefore, considered necessary to study the reaction of phenacyl bromide with a dibasic molecule. Search for literature did not reveal any work having been done on the subject. Moreover, since, *o*-PDA is known to exist in hydrogen bonded claw like structure, it was considered worthwhile to study the effect of different solvents on the structural nature of *o*-PDA in its reaction with phenacyl bromide.

EXPERIMENTAL

The phenylene diamines (PDA s) were purified by repeated crystallisation from benzene. AnalaR methanol was used. Ethanol, acetone, nitrobenzene, *n*-propyl alcohol, *n*-butyl alcohol were purified by standard methods.

Phenacyl bromide (0.02*M*) and PDAs (0.04*M*) solutions were prepared in different solvents and were thermostated ($\pm 0.1^\circ$). Equal volumes (5 ml.) of each reactant were taken in a previously thermostated conductance cell and the readings of resistance were recorded at different intervals of time by a conductance bridge.

The specific reaction rate values were evaluated by the method already reported¹. The energy and entropy of activation values were calculated. The results have been given in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

Reaction of Phenacyl Bromide and Aniline and Phenylenediamines

Amines	$k \times 10^3$ in lit.mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹				E in Kcals/mole	log PZ	ΔS^\ddagger in E.U.
	32.5°	35°	37.5°	40°			
<i>o</i> -PDA	2.40	3.19	4.03	5.23	21.10	12.37	- 2.03
Aniline	2.554	3.36	4.32	5.28	19.81	11.49	- 6.08
<i>m</i> -PDA	51.84	62.86	76.08	89.76	14.49	9.02	-17.46
<i>p</i> -PDA	1241.00	1440.00	1727.00	2037.00	12.67	9.09	-17.13

TABLE II
Solvent Effect

Name of solvent	$k \times 10^3$ in lit. mole ⁻¹ sec. ⁻¹					E in Kcals/ mole	Log PZ	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ in E.U.	ΔF^\ddagger Kcals/ mole
	30°	32.5°	35°	37.5°	40°				
Nitrobenzene	—	2.40	3.19	4.03	5.23	21.1	12.37	2.03	21.70
Methanol	2.64	3.12	4.08	4.8		14.95	8.15	21.46	21.56
<i>n</i> -Butanol	4.32	5.76	7.20	8.64		18.57	10.96	8.52	21.19
<i>n</i> -Propanol	6.24	8.06	9.60	12.48		17.22	10.12	12.4	20.93
Ethanol	7.68	9.88	12.48	15.36		15.99	9.37	15.85	20.87
Benzyl alcohol	6.08	7.49	8.96	11.04		16.07	9.28	16.26	21.07
Acetone	91.72	97.92	108.48	—		7.54	4.35	38.97	19.54

DISCUSSION

The reaction between PDAs and phenacyl bromide proceeds in the following manner :

The concentration used for PDAs is twice that of phenacyl bromide. So there is greater probability of the phenacyl bromide meeting a fresh molecule of PDA than the same molecule, which has already reacted once. So probably, both the amine groups of the same molecule do not react as is evident from the straight line of time resistance plot. Moreover, the second amino group may immediately react with H^+ since H^+ , being lighter than the solvent cage, may be stopped or reflected back by the collision with a molecule of the solvent and hence get attached to the second $-\text{NH}_2$ group.

The values for the energy of activation and entropy of activation suggest that the reaction in respect of meta- and para- PDAs is only electronic in nature since the entropies of activation values remain constant. But in case of ortho- PDA, both energy and entropy of activation values increase considerably. In ortho-PDA, there is H-bond formation. The reaction with phenacyl bromide may involve rupture of hydrogen bond thus explaining the energy of activation being higher in this case than that for aniline. The two to three fold decrease in the entropy of activation values for meta- and para- isomers in comparison to that for aniline can be explained when the statistical factor is taken into account.

The rate ratio for *m*-phenylene diamine and aniline is 25 : 1 and between *p*-phenylene diamine and aniline is 600 : 1.

Solvent effect : The kinetics of reaction of ortho-PDA and phenacyl bromide have also been studied in various aprotic and dipolar aprotic solvents, and the results are given in Table II. The general effect of changing the solvent is to bring about a change in both E and A, the two changes being in the same direction. The energy and entropy of activation values have been linearly fitted to the equation :

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = \Delta H_0^\ddagger + \beta \Delta S^\ddagger.$$

So a compensation between activation parameters has been observed²⁻⁵. The value of ΔH_0^\ddagger has been found to be 21.75 Kcals/mole. ΔH^\ddagger values are also linearly related to ΔF^\ddagger values with a slope of +6.4⁶. The points for methanol and benzyl alcohol showed considerable deviation from the straight line. The values of energy of activation in methanol and benzyl alcohol should have been 20.8 and 17.5 Kcals/mole respectively. The energy of activation in methanol is low though the rate data are not proportionately higher. The hydrogen bonded structure of ortho-PDA is surrounded by the methanol cage through hydrogen bond formation. In order to react with phenacyl bromide it has to overcome the potential of the solvent cage and so the reactivity is low. But the transition state once formed has a lower energy because the charge developed on nitrogen gets dissipated quickly to the solvent system in the following manner :

But in case of ethanol, propanol, butanol etc., such a situation if it arises, would take place at the cost of rotational freedom of C-C bond of the alcohol. The value for benzyl alcohol also deviates from the line (ΔH^\ddagger and ΔF^\ddagger plot) but not to the same extent as for methanol because in its case the benzyl group is relatively flat (and has less rotational freedom due to σ bonded resonance of $-\text{CH}_2$ -group and benzene ring).

The values of rate constants are low in nitrobenzene but very high in acetone. This may be due to an enrichment of the transition state in acetone. In nitrobenzene probably, ortho-PDA does not exist as a hydrogen bonded structure. Since, a deepening of colour has been observed while preparing the solution, a charge-transfer complex may be formed between o-PDA and nitrobenzene. The lower rate of reactivity in nitrobenzene may be ascribed to this effect.

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